

Nigeria's Foreign Relations and Soft Power Diplomacy Amidst Cybercrime

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Abstract

This research paper examines the multifaceted impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign relations, exploring its economic, political, security, and soft power dimensions. Drawing on realism and constructivism, the study investigates how cybercrime, originating from within Nigeria, affects the country's diplomatic ties, economic partnerships, and international reputation. Through a qualitative methodology, the research analyzes government documents, academic studies, and media reports to uncover the underlying causes of cybercrime in Nigeria and assess the effectiveness of existing countermeasures. The findings reveal that cybercrime has had a detrimental impact on Nigeria's foreign relations, hindering foreign direct investment, disrupting trade relations, and straining diplomatic ties. The country's reputation as a cybercrime hub has also eroded its soft power, making it difficult to leverage technology and the Internet for positive diplomatic engagement. The study identifies key drivers of cybercrime in Nigeria, including socioeconomic factors like unemployment and poverty, as well as technological vulnerabilities stemming from rapid digitization and insufficient cybersecurity infrastructure. The research concludes by offering recommendations for policymakers, diplomats, and cybersecurity professionals to mitigate the negative impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign relations. These recommendations include strengthening legal frameworks, investing in cybersecurity infrastructure and capacity building, promoting public awareness and education, fostering international cooperation, and addressing the root causes of cybercrime through socioeconomic interventions. Adopting a comprehensive and multi-faceted approach can help Nigeria enhance its cyber resilience, protect its national interests, and improve its standing in the international community.

Keywords: *Cybercrimes, Foreign Relations, Hacking, Cybersecurity, International Relations*

1. Introduction and Background

The 21st century has witnessed a dramatic surge in cybercrimes globally, posing significant threats to national and international security (Chen et al., 2023). Cyberattacks, ranging from ransomware to data breaches and cyber espionage, have become increasingly common, with the cost of cybercrime estimated to reach \$10.5 trillion annually by 2025 (Morgan, 2020). As nations become increasingly reliant on digital infrastructures for economic, social, and political activities, the potential for disruption and harm from cyberattacks has escalated massively.

Nigeria, a rapidly developing country with a fast-growing digital expansion, is not immune to this trend. The country's growing reliance on the Internet for economic activities, social interactions, and political engagement has made it an attractive target for cybercriminals (Omodunbi et al., 2016). Reports indicate a significant increase in cyberattacks originating from or targeting Africa, encompassing a wide range of activities, including financial fraud, identity theft, and cyber espionage (Jaiyeola, 2023a). Recent incidents involving a fintech glitch at a Chinese backed fintech, which led

to the erroneous disbursement of funds, and the unauthorized access to the National Identity Management Commission (NIMC) database by a private website underscore the growing vulnerabilities in the Nigerian digital ecosystem.

Despite the growing recognition of cybercrime as a global threat, there remains a limited understanding of its specific implications for Nigeria's foreign relations. Existing research has primarily focused on the technical aspects of cyberattacks or their economic consequences within the country. There needs to be more studies investigating how cybercrimes impact Nigeria's diplomatic relationships, its ability to project soft power through technology, and its standing within the international community.

This research paper aims to address this gap by examining the multifaceted impact of cybercrimes on Nigeria's foreign relations. This study aims to offer a thorough analysis of how cybercrime impacts Nigeria's diplomatic landscape by examining its economic, political, and security dimensions.

1.1 The State of Cybercrime in Nigeria

Nigeria has garnered an unfortunate reputation as a significant source of cybercriminal activities (Bruce et al., 2024). A 2023 report by the University of Oxford and the University of New South Wales ranked Nigeria 5th among the world's top cybercrime hotspots (Bruce et al., 2024). The study highlighted Nigeria's involvement in various cybercrimes, including technical products/services (like malware), attacks and extortion, data/identity theft, scams, and money laundering. This ranking underscores the seriousness of the cybercrime issue in Nigeria and its potential to tarnish the country's international image.

Specific instances of cybercrime originating from Nigeria have made headlines in recent years. The recent Chinese-backed fintech glitch, where customers received value for pending transactions due to a system error, led to significant financial losses for the company and highlighted the vulnerability of digital monetary systems in the country (Olowogboyega, 2024). Additionally, the unauthorized access to the NIMC database by a private website, potentially compromising millions of Nigerians' sensitive personal information, exposed the country's weak cybersecurity infrastructure and raised concerns about data protection and privacy (Ojukwu, 2024). These incidents have further cemented Nigeria's reputation as a cybercrime hub. In 2020, a Nigerian national was extradited to the United States to face charges related to a massive business email compromise scheme that resulted in losses of over \$1.7 billion (U.S. Department of Justice, 2020). Additionally, Nigerian cybercriminals have been implicated in various romance scams targeting individuals worldwide, causing significant financial and emotional distress to victims.

The prevalence of cybercrime in Nigeria can be attributed to several factors, including a lack of robust cybersecurity infrastructure, limited law enforcement capacity, and socioeconomic challenges that incentivize illicit activities (Bamidele et.al., 2023). Moreover, the anonymous nature of the internet and the transnational reach of cyberattacks make it difficult to trace and prosecute perpetrators, further exacerbating the problem. The Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) report revealed that Nigeria loses over \$500 million annually to cybercrime (Sibe, 2024).

1.2 The Impact on Nigeria's Reputation and Soft Power

The persistent association of Nigeria with cybercrime has had a detrimental impact on the country's reputation and its ability to project soft power through technology and the internet. Soft power, defined as the ability to influence others through attraction and persuasion rather than coercion, increasingly relies on digital platforms for cultural exchange, knowledge dissemination, and

diplomatic engagement (Nye, 2004). However, Nigeria's cybercrime problem constantly impacts the success and efforts to improve its credibility and attractiveness in these arenas.

The negative perception of Nigeria as a cybercrime haven can impact the socioeconomic development of Nigeria as it tarnishes the image of the country at the global scale, deters foreign investments, hindering the country's efforts to position itself as a technological hub in Africa (Jack & Ene, 2016). It can also make it difficult for Nigerian businesses and individuals to establish trust and credibility in online interactions, creating economic growth and development barriers.

Furthermore, the association with cybercrime can undermine Nigeria's diplomatic efforts by creating distrust and skepticism among international partners (Emmanuella, 2021). It can make it more difficult for Nigeria to negotiate favorable agreements, build alliances, and participate effectively in international forums. In essence, cybercrime acts as a counterweight to Nigeria's attempts to leverage technology and the internet for soft power, ultimately diminishing its influence on the global stage.

2. Statement of Problem

Nigeria's growing prominence in cybercrime activities presents a significant challenge to its foreign relations. While the country strives to leverage technology and the internet for economic growth and diplomatic influence, its association with cybercrime undermines these efforts (Okoru & Oluku, 2024). This negative perception not only deters foreign investment and collaboration but also erodes trust and credibility in Nigeria's digital engagements (Jack & Ene, 2016).

The central problem addressed in this paper is the extent to which cybercrime is eroding Nigeria's diplomatic standing and hindering its ability to leverage technology for soft power. Specifically, this research investigates:

1. **Economic Impact:** How does the perception of Nigeria as a cybercrime hub affect foreign direct investment (FDI), trade relations, and economic partnerships?
2. **Political Impact:** How does cybercrime influence Nigeria's diplomatic relationships, its ability to negotiate favorable agreements, and its participation in international forums?
3. **Security Impact:** How do cyberattacks originating from Nigeria affect the country's national security and its cooperation with international partners on cybersecurity issues?
4. **Soft Power Impact:** How does cybercrime hinder Nigeria's ability to project soft power through technology, cultural exchange, and digital diplomacy?

This research seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign relations by addressing the aforementioned questions. The findings will inform policymakers, diplomats, and cybersecurity experts on the urgency of addressing cybercrime to safeguard Nigeria's national interests and enhance its global standing.

3. Research Questions and Objectives

To comprehensively address the central problem of cybercrime's erosion of Nigeria's diplomatic standing, this research will be guided by the following specific questions and objectives:

1. How have cybercrimes originating from Nigeria impacted the country's foreign policy priorities, bilateral relationships, and engagement with international organizations, particularly in terms of economic and political consequences?
2. To what extent has the perception of Nigeria as a hub for cybercrime affected the country's ability to leverage technology and the internet as tools for soft power diplomacy?

3. What policy and strategic recommendations can be implemented to mitigate the negative impact of cybercrimes on Nigeria's foreign relations and enhance the country's international image in the digital age?

This study aims to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the multifaceted impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign relations by addressing the above-listed questions. The findings will inform policymakers, diplomats, and cybersecurity experts in developing effective strategies to mitigate cyber threats, enhance diplomatic engagements, and leverage technology for positive soft power projection.

4. Literature Review

The intersection of cybercrime, cybersecurity, and international relations has become a burgeoning field of study, reflecting the growing importance of digital technologies in shaping global politics and diplomacy. Scholarly literature on cybercrimes has explored their diverse manifestations, from financial fraud and identity theft to cyber espionage and critical infrastructure attacks (Brenner, 2009). Cybersecurity research, on the other hand, has focused on developing technical and policy solutions to mitigate cyber threats and enhance resilience (Safitra et al., 2023).

In the realm of international relations, studies have examined how cyberattacks can escalate tensions between nations, disrupt diplomatic communications, and even trigger real-world conflicts ((Mezue et al., 2024). The concept of cyber power, encompassing both offensive and defensive capabilities in cyberspace, has emerged as a significant factor in shaping geopolitical dynamics (Geopolitical Factors Shaping the Future of the Cyber Domain, 2023).

While there is a growing body of research on the general impact of cybercrime on international relations, the specific effects on Nigeria's foreign policy remain under-explored. Existing studies have primarily focused on the domestic consequences of cybercrime in Nigeria, such as economic losses, security challenges (Bamidele et al., 2023), and the role of sociological and technological factors in the proliferation of cybercrime (Felix, 2016). However, there is a lack of research investigating how cybercrime specifically emanating from Nigeria affects the country's diplomatic relationships, its ability to project soft power, and its international reputation as a whole.

Some studies have touched upon the broader implications of cybercrime for Nigeria, highlighting the potential for cyberattacks to undermine political stability, economic development, and regional security (Tsado et al., 2023). However, these studies often lack a nuanced understanding of the specific challenges and opportunities facing Nigeria, a country with a unique geopolitical position and a complex cybercrime-infested society.

Nigeria's cybercrime situation is unique and multifaceted. The country has gained notoriety for being a hub of cybercriminal activities, with the infamous "419" scams (advance fee fraud) originating from the country (Adomi & Igun, 2008). This has led to a negative perception of Nigeria on the world stage, affecting its economic growth and diplomatic relations.

Several factors contribute to the prevalence of cybercrime in Nigeria. These include high unemployment rates, poverty, and a lack of awareness about cybersecurity (Amos, 2021). The rise of cybercafes, often poorly regulated, has also provided a breeding ground for cybercriminals (Osho & Adepoju, 2016). Additionally, the lack of robust cybersecurity infrastructure and limited law enforcement capacity has made it difficult to combat cybercrime effectively (Aminu Muhammad Auwal, 2023).

4.1 Cybersecurity Measures and Policies in Nigeria

Nigeria's cybersecurity scene has seen significant developments in recent years, driven by the increasing prevalence and sophistication of cyber threats. The government has taken several steps to enhance its cybersecurity measures and policies, although challenges and criticisms persist.

The cornerstone of Nigeria's cybersecurity legal framework remains the Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act of 2015. This Act criminalizes various cyber offences, including hacking, identity theft, and cyberstalking, and outlines penalties for offenders. However, critics argue that the Act is not comprehensive enough and lacks provisions for emerging threats like ransomware and cryptojacking (Titilola, 2024).

The National Cybersecurity Policy and Strategy (NCPS) 2021, launched in February 2021, represents a significant step forward. The NCPS outlines a comprehensive approach to cybersecurity, encompassing critical infrastructure protection, data protection, cybercrime prevention, and capacity building. It emphasizes a multi-stakeholder approach, involving government agencies, the private sector, and civil society organizations (Ekekwe, 2021).

In line with the NCPS, the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) has been actively involved in developing and enforcing cybersecurity regulations. In 2019, NITDA issued the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR), which aims to protect the personal data of Nigerian citizens and ensure compliance with international data protection standards.

Despite these efforts, challenges remain. The implementation and enforcement of cybersecurity laws and regulations remain inconsistent, and there is a lack of adequate resources and technical expertise to effectively combat cyber threats.

In conclusion, while Nigeria has made strides in developing cybersecurity measures and policies, there is still much work to be done. Addressing the evolving nature of cyber threats requires a continuous and adaptive approach, involving collaboration between government agencies, the private sector, and civil society organizations.

4.2 The Impact of Cybercrime on Nigeria's National Security & Digital Economy

Cybercrime poses a significant threat to Nigeria's national security. It can disrupt critical national infrastructure, such as power grids and communication networks (Kpae, 2020). Cyberattacks can also compromise sensitive government data, leading to economic losses and undermining public trust (Ibrahim, 2019). Furthermore, cybercrime can facilitate other security threats, such as terrorism and insurgency, by providing a platform for communication and coordination (Iwenwanne, 2021).

The rise of cybercrime in Nigeria has had a detrimental impact on the country's digital economy. Cyberattacks on businesses and financial institutions have resulted in significant financial losses (Ibrahim, 2019). The fear of cybercrime has also deterred foreign investment and hindered the growth of e-commerce in the country.

While existing research has shed light on various aspects of cybercrime and cybersecurity in Nigeria, there remains a gap in understanding the specific effects of cybercrimes on Nigeria's foreign relations. This research paper aims to fill this gap by examining how cybercrime impacts Nigeria's diplomatic relationships, its ability to project soft power, and its international reputation. These under-researched areas can further be explored, as it will significantly contribute to the broader discourse on cybercrime and its implications for national security and international relations.

5. Theoretical Framework

To understand the complex relationship between cybercrimes and Nigeria's foreign relations, this study adopts a theoretical framework that combines elements of realism and constructivism. These two prominent international relations theories offer complementary perspectives on how states interact in the international arena and how their actions are shaped by both material and ideational factors.

5.1 Realism

Realism, a dominant theory in international relations, posits that states are primarily motivated by self-interest and the pursuit of power (Mearsheimer, 2021). In the context of cybercrime, realism suggests that Nigeria's response to cyber threats is driven by a desire to protect its national security and economic interests. The Nigerian government's efforts to enact cybersecurity legislation, such as the Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act of 2015, strengthen law enforcement agencies like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), and collaborate with international partners can be seen as realist measures aimed at safeguarding the nation's power and influence in the international system (Aytogo, 2022).

Realism also highlights the role of power dynamics in shaping international relations. Nigeria's vulnerability to cyberattacks, particularly from more technologically advanced nations, can be seen as a reflection of its relative power disadvantage in cyberspace. This vulnerability can limit Nigeria's ability to deter cyber aggression and may necessitate reliance on international cooperation for protection, as advocated by Mezue et al. (2024), who emphasize the importance of a "collective response" to cyber threats.

5.2 Constructivism

Constructivism, on the other hand, emphasizes the role of ideas, norms, and identities in shaping state behavior (Mengshu, 2020). In the context of cybercrime, constructivism suggests that Nigeria's reputation as a cybercrime hub is not merely a reflection of its material capabilities but also a product of social constructions and perceptions. The negative image associated with Nigerian cybercriminals, such as the "Yahoo Boys" phenomenon, can influence how other nations perceive and interact with Nigeria, potentially leading to diplomatic isolation and economic sanctions (Aborisade, 2022). This aligns with the study's focus on how cybercrime affects Nigeria's international reputation and soft power.

Constructivism also highlights the importance of norms and shared understandings in international relations. The growing international consensus on the need to combat cybercrime, as evidenced by international agreements like the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, can create pressure on Nigeria to address the issue and conform to international norms of responsible state behavior in cyberspace (Aytogo, 2022).

This study adopts a synthesized approach that combines elements of realism and constructivism to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of cybercrimes on Nigeria's foreign relations. While acknowledging the importance of self-interest and power dynamics, this approach also recognizes the role of ideas, norms, and identities in shaping state behavior. This aligns with the research conducted by Tsado et al. (2023), which emphasizes the need for a multi-faceted approach to understanding and addressing cybercrime in Nigeria.

This research seeks to answer the following questions through the integration of these two theoretical perspectives:

1. How do Nigeria's national interests and power considerations shape its response to cyber threats, particularly in the context of its foreign policy priorities and bilateral relationships?
2. How does the perception of Nigeria as a cybercrime hub, influenced by factors such as the "Yahoo Boys" phenomenon and media portrayals, affect its diplomatic relationships and international standing?
3. What role do international norms and cooperation, as exemplified by the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, play in shaping Nigeria's cybersecurity policies and practices, and how can these be leveraged to enhance the country's cybersecurity efforts and international image?

Addressing these questions through a synthesized theoretical lens helps provide a nuanced analysis of the complex relationship between cybercrime and Nigeria's foreign relations, drawing on both material and ideational factors to explain state behavior in the digital age. This approach will contribute to a deeper understanding of how cybercrime affects Nigeria's diplomatic positioning and inform the development of effective strategies to mitigate these threats and enhance the country's international standing.

6. Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research methodology to investigate the intricate relationship between cybercrimes and Nigeria's foreign relations. Qualitative methods were well-suited for exploring complex social phenomena, such as the impact of cybercrime on diplomatic relations, as they allowed for in-depth analysis of contextual factors, perceptions, and meanings (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015).

6.1 Data Collection Techniques

The research utilized a triangulation of data sources to ensure a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the issue. This triangulation involved the following data collection techniques: **Document Analysis:** A systematic review of relevant government reports, policy documents, legislative acts, and official statements was conducted. These documents provided insights into Nigeria's official stance on cybercrime, its policy responses, and its engagement with international partners on cybersecurity issues. **Academic Literature Review:** A thorough review of scholarly articles, books, and research papers on cybercrime, cybersecurity, and international relations was undertaken. This helped to contextualize the Nigerian case within the broader academic discourse and identify relevant theoretical frameworks and empirical findings. **Media Analysis:** News articles, opinion pieces, and editorials from reputable national and international media outlets were analyzed to gauge public discourse on cybercrime in Nigeria, assess media framing of the issue, and identify potential biases or gaps in reporting.

6.2 Sampling Strategy and Selection Criteria

The selection of data sources was guided by the following criteria:

- **Relevance:** Documents, studies, and media articles that directly addressed the impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign relations were prioritized.
- **Credibility:** Only sources from reputable government agencies, academic institutions, and established media outlets were included.

- **Timeliness:** The focus was on recent publications and reports to ensure the analysis reflected the current state of cybercrime and its implications for Nigeria's foreign relations.

6.3 Ethical Considerations and Limitations

Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the research process. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained for all individuals mentioned in media articles or other sources, and any sensitive information was handled with discretion. The study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects, as outlined by relevant institutional review boards. The research methodology had inherent limitations. The reliance on secondary data sources may have introduced biases or gaps in information. Additionally, the qualitative nature of the study may limit the generalizability of findings to other contexts. However, the combination of data sources and the rigorous analysis of diverse perspectives helped to mitigate these limitations and ensure the validity and reliability of the research findings.

7. Discussion of Findings

The analysis reveals a complex interplay between cybercrime and Nigeria's foreign relations, with significant implications for the nation's economic, political, and social standing. Cybercrime has had a profound and multifaceted impact on Nigeria's economy and political landscape. Its economic repercussions are particularly evident in the decline of foreign direct investment (FDI). Nigeria's reputation as a hub for cybercrime has fostered an environment of distrust among international investors, resulting in decreased FDI inflows. This decline not only impedes economic growth but also limits Nigeria's capacity to leverage foreign capital for developmental initiatives and technological advancements.

7.1 Economic and Political Impact of Cybercrime in Nigeria

Economically, the consequences of cybercrime are evident in the financial losses suffered by businesses and individuals. A recent report by Kaspersky revealed that Nigeria recorded the second-highest number of cyberattacks in Africa in the first quarter of 2023 (Jaiyeola, 2023a). These attacks, ranging from ransomware to phishing scams, have resulted in significant financial losses for Nigerian businesses, deterring both domestic and foreign investment. Similarly, the Cyber Security Experts Association of Nigeria (CSEAN) reported that phishing attacks on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) increased by 87% in 2022, leading to substantial financial losses and operational disruptions (Udi, 2023).

The 2023 Nigerian general elections brought the political impact of cybercrime into sharp focus. The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) reported experiencing over 12.9 million cyberattacks during the elections, primarily in the form of distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks aimed at disrupting the electoral process (Izuaka, 2023). While these attacks did not significantly impact the election results, they highlighted the vulnerability of Nigeria's critical infrastructure to cyber threats and raised concerns about the integrity of future elections.

Furthermore, the rise of disinformation and fake news propagated through online platforms has become a significant concern in Nigeria's political arena. The spread of false information during the elections, often amplified by social media, had the potential to incite violence and undermine public trust in the electoral process (Imam, 2024).

The political impact of cybercrime extends beyond elections. Recent reports indicate a surge in cyberattacks targeting government agencies, with the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) issuing warnings about hacking activities aimed at government digital services

(Jaiyeola, 2023b). These attacks not only threaten the confidentiality and integrity of government data but also undermine public confidence in the government's ability to protect sensitive information and deliver essential services.

The economic and political impact of cybercrime in Nigeria is undeniable and multifaceted. It not only poses a threat to businesses and individuals but also undermines the integrity of democratic processes and national security. Addressing this challenge requires a concerted effort from government, businesses, and civil society to strengthen cybersecurity infrastructure, enhance public awareness, and promote international cooperation in combating cyber threats.

7.2 Security and Soft Power Impact of Cybercrime in Nigeria

Cyberattacks originating from Nigeria have raised significant national security concerns, both domestically and internationally. These attacks have exposed vulnerabilities in critical infrastructure, such as the power grid and financial systems, making them susceptible to disruption and sabotage. The potential consequences of such attacks are far-reaching, including economic losses, social unrest, and political instability. For instance, in 2022, a cyberattack on a major Nigerian bank disrupted financial services for millions of customers, causing widespread panic and economic disruption (George, 2023). This incident aligns with Kpae (2020) argument that cybercrime can lead to the collapse of critical national infrastructures.

Internationally, cyberattacks attributed to Nigerian actors have strained the country's relationships with other nations and undermined its efforts to combat transnational cybercrime. The negative perception of Nigeria as a source of cyber threats can lead to diplomatic isolation and hinder cooperation on cybersecurity issues. This is evident in the increased scrutiny and stricter visa requirements imposed on Nigerian travellers by some countries due to concerns about cybercrime.

Moreover, cybercrime has significantly impacted Nigeria's soft power, which is the ability to influence others through attraction and persuasion rather than coercion (Nye, 2004). The country's reputation as a cybercrime hub has tarnished its image and made it difficult to leverage technology and the internet for positive soft power projection. This negative perception can deter cultural exchange, knowledge sharing, and digital diplomacy initiatives, ultimately diminishing Nigeria's influence on the global stage. For example, the prevalence of online scams originating from Nigeria has made it difficult for legitimate Nigerian businesses and entrepreneurs to establish trust and credibility in the international market. This aligns with the study's position that cybercrimes in Nigeria impact the country's potential to harness technology and the internet as a reliable soft power to foster diplomatic efforts.

A recent incident in 2024 involving the National Identity Management Commission (NIMC) further exemplifies the detrimental impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's reputation and security. A private website, XpressVerify, gained unauthorized access to the personal data of millions of Nigerians, including their National Identification Numbers (NINs) (Ojukwu, 2024). This breach not only compromised the privacy and security of Nigerian citizens but also raised serious concerns about the government's ability to protect sensitive data. The incident led to public outcry and further tarnished Nigeria's image as a country struggling to control cybercrime.

In another incident, the Chinese-backed fintech giant faced a system glitch that allowed customers to receive value for unsuccessful transactions, resulting in a loss of ₦714 million (Olowogboyega, 2024). While the company attempted to recover the funds, this incident highlighted the vulnerabilities of digital financial platforms and the potential for financial losses due to cyber incidents.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1 Conclusion

This research has illuminated the multifaceted impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign relations. The findings underscore that cybercrime is not merely a domestic issue but a transnational challenge with profound implications for Nigeria's economic, political, and social standing in the international arena. The erosion of foreign direct investment strained diplomatic ties, and the tarnishing of Nigeria's image as a reliable and trustworthy partner are all consequences of the unchecked proliferation of cybercriminal activities originating from within the country.

The study's findings also highlight the complex interplay of sociological and technological factors that contribute to the persistence of cybercrime in Nigeria. High unemployment rates, inadequate education, and the cultural acceptance of cybercrime within certain segments of society create a fertile ground for cybercriminals to thrive. Simultaneously, the rapid digitization of the Nigerian economy, coupled with inadequate cybersecurity infrastructure and a lack of awareness among the general populace, exacerbates the nation's vulnerability to cyber threats.

To mitigate the detrimental impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign relations, a multi-pronged approach is imperative. This approach must address both the root causes of cybercrime and the immediate challenges it poses to the nation's security and international standing.

8.2 Recommendations

To effectively combat the escalating cybercrime rates in Nigeria, a multi-faceted and collaborative approach is essential. This requires active participation from various government agencies and stakeholders, with a particular emphasis on clarifying roles and responsibilities to avoid duplication of efforts and optimize resource utilization.

1. **Strengthening Legal and Regulatory Frameworks:** The Nigerian government should prioritize the continuous review and amendment of existing cybersecurity legislation, such as the Cybercrime Act of 2015, to ensure it remains adaptable and relevant to the ever-evolving nature of cyber threats. This includes addressing loopholes, enhancing enforcement mechanisms, and promoting inter-agency collaboration to ensure a cohesive and unified response to cybercrime.
2. **Addressing Socioeconomic Factors:** To tackle the root causes of cybercrime, the Nigerian government must address the underlying socioeconomic factors that drive individuals towards cybercriminal activities. This includes investing in education and job creation programs to provide alternative pathways for economic empowerment and reduce the allure of cybercrime.
3. **Establish a National Fraud Registry:** Collaborate with financial institutions to create a standardized registry of fraudsters and fraud cases, accessible to all financial institutions. This registry should be regularly updated and publicly accessible, incentivizing institutions to report incidents without fear of reprisal.
4. **Cybersecurity Audits and Compliance:** Mandate and rigorously enforce regular cybersecurity audits for all financial institutions, ensuring compliance with evolving international standards and best practices. Non-compliance should be met with appropriate penalties to incentivize robust security measures.
5. **Organize Cybersecurity Hackathons:** Leverage the expertise of technology enthusiasts by organizing hackathons focused on developing innovative solutions to counter cyber fraud. These events can foster a collaborative environment and generate novel ideas for enhancing cybersecurity.
6. **Launch Multilingual Advocacy Campaigns:** Invest in public awareness campaigns across various media platforms, including radio, television, and social media, to educate the public about cybercrime trends, prevention strategies, and reporting mechanisms. These campaigns

should be tailored to different demographics, including the elderly, who are often targeted by cybercriminals.

7. **Enhanced International Collaboration:** Expand existing international collaborations to include not only law enforcement agencies but also cybersecurity firms and research institutions. This can facilitate the exchange of threat intelligence, tools, and techniques, as well as joint operations against transnational cybercrime networks.
8. **Specialized Training and Certification:** Invest in continuous training and certification programs for NPF National Cybercrime Center officers to keep them abreast of the latest cyber threats and investigative techniques. This should include training on emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and blockchain, which are increasingly being leveraged by cybercriminals.
9. **Memorandum of Understanding (MoU):** Establish a formal MoU between the NPF - NCCC, Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), and other relevant agencies to clearly delineate their respective roles and responsibilities in combating cybercrime. This will minimize overlap, streamline investigations, and ensure a coordinated response to cyber threats.
10. **Cybercrime Joint Task Forces:** Create joint task forces comprising officers from different agencies, cybersecurity professionals as well as properly vetted volunteer networks to identify and investigate complex cybercrime cases that require multidisciplinary expertise. This will facilitate information sharing, expedite investigations, and enhance the effectiveness of law enforcement efforts.

With these recommendations and driving a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement, Nigeria can significantly enhance its cybersecurity posture and effectively combat the growing threat of cybercrime. The findings of this research have broader implications for understanding the intersection of cybercrime and diplomacy in the digital age. As cyber threats continue to evolve and transcend national borders, the need for international cooperation and a multi-stakeholder approach to cybersecurity becomes increasingly critical.

Furthermore, future studies should examine the impact of cybercrime on Nigeria's foreign policy decision-making processes and its engagement with regional and international organizations. This can provide valuable insights into how cyber threats are shaping Nigeria's role in the global arena and its ability to achieve its foreign policy objectives. Addressing these research gaps can help gain a more comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between cybercrime and foreign relations, not only in Nigeria but also in other countries struggling with similar challenges. This knowledge is essential for developing effective policies and strategies to mitigate cyber threats and promote a more secure and stable international environment.

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